

Reactions of Aliphatic Acetals with *N*-Chlorosaccharin : A Kinetic Study

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The oxidation of aliphatic acetals as well as aromatic acetals with peracetic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid¹ or with chromic acid in aqueous acetic acid medium² yielded corresponding esters as the products. A perusal of literature reveals that *N*-halo amides and imides are versatile oxidising agents for a variety of organic compounds³. We now report the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aliphatic acetals by NCSA in aqueous acetic acid.

Results and Discussion

The salient features of kinetics of oxidation of aliphatic acetals by NCSA in HOAc-H₂O medium are given in Table 1. The reactions were conducted in HOAc-H₂O medium since the substrates are of limited solubility in pure water. The results are presented in Tables 2-4.

TABLE 1 SALIENT FEATURES OF KINETICS OF OXIDATION OF ACETALS BY NCSA

Experiment	Observation	Inference
Time vs [NCSA]	Linear	First order with respect to [NCSA]
[acetal] >> [NCSA]	(<i>r</i> > 0.98)	Zero order with respect to [acetal]
[Acetal] vs <i>k</i> ₁	No effect	Rate determining step involves dipole-dipole interaction
log <i>k</i> ₂ vs (<i>D</i> -1)/(2 <i>D</i> +1)	Linear	No base catalysis
Addition of pyridine	No change in rate	No specific chloride ion effect
log <i>k</i> ₂ vs log [H ⁺]	Rate dependence on [H ⁺] is 0.6 for HClO ₄ and 0.5 for H ₂ SO ₄	
Effect of chloride		No specific chloride ion effect

D = Dielectric constants of HOAc-H₂O mixture (10 to 25%)

TABLE 2-DEPENDENCE OF REACTION RATE ON SOLVENT COMPOSITION

[Acetal] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³, [NCSA] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Ionic strength = 0.2 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 308 ± 0.1 K

Acetal	10 ⁴ <i>k</i> ₁ (s ⁻¹)				
	% HOAc <i>D</i> *	10%	15%	20%	25%
AEA	1.52	1.24	1.10	0.90	0.90
AnPA	1.34	1.07	0.86	0.60	0.60
AnBA	1.24	1.00	0.80	0.71	0.71
AtBA	1.12	0.80	0.71	0.60	0.60
AtBA	1.92	1.58	0.93	0.72	0.72

Table-2 (contd)

PEA	2.01	1.62	1.30	1.10
nBEA	2.30	2.10	1.70	1.40
mCAEA	1.12	1.08	0.97	0.82
dCAEA	1.04	0.96	0.77	0.68
ABA	2.25	1.36	1.03	0.69
mCABA	2.15	1.06	0.98	0.70

* Ref 7

TABLE 3

[AEA] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [NCSA] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Ionic strength = 0.2 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 308 ± 0.1 K, Solvent 10% HOAc - 90% H₂O (v/v)

Time in min	<i>V</i> _t	(<i>V</i> _t - <i>V</i> _∞)	2 + log(<i>V</i> _t - <i>V</i> _∞)
10	8.7	8.5	2.9294
20	7.9	7.7	2.8864
30	7.2	7.0	2.8450
40	6.8	6.6	2.8195
50	6.3	6.1	2.7853
60	5.7	5.5	2.7403
70	5.1	4.9	2.6901
80	4.6	4.4	2.6434
90	4.4	4.2	2.6232
100	3.9	3.7	2.5682

*V*_∞ = 0.2
*k*₁ = 1.52 × 10⁻⁴ s⁻¹
r = 0.997

TABLE 4-DEPENDENCE OF REACTION RATE ON SOLVENT COMPOSITION

[Acetal] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [NCSA] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Ionic strength = 0.2 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 308 ± 0.1 K

HOAc %	<i>D</i> *	$\frac{(D-1)}{(2D+1)}$	10 ² <i>k</i> ₂	3 + log <i>k</i> ₂
10	67.00	0.4888	0.76	0.8808
15	63.00	0.4881	0.62	0.7923
20	60.25	0.4876	0.55	0.7403
25	56.25	0.4867	0.45	0.6532

r = 0.997 *Ref 7

The rate law consistent with the experimental results is

$$-\frac{d[\text{NCSA}]}{dt} = k [\text{NCSA}] [\text{H}^+]^x$$

The rate enhancement due to the addition of H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ can be traced to the effect of the H⁺ of the mineral acids on chloronium ion⁴.

The values of specific rate constants (k_s) for the rate equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{NCSA}]}{dt} = k_s [\text{NCSA}]$$

can be calculated for the oxidation of acetals with NCSA. The kinetic scheme is formulated involving chloronium ion⁴ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The kinetic results (Table 2) reveal that there is not much difference in rate constant while changing the C-C chain-length or substituting it with benzyl group in alcohol moiety. Moreover, neither the introduction of chlorine atom nor replacing the aldehyde part with its higher homologues bring about appreciable change in the rate. The results can be rationalised by the formulation of a slow step involving dipolar entities rather than ionic species. Further, the transition states for all the acetals may have similar structure and polarity. This is supported by the fact that the variation in the values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for various acetals is not appreciable.

Experimental

Acetaldehyde diethylacetal (AEA) and dichloroacetaldehyde diethylacetal (dCAEA) (Merck) were used. Acetaldehyde di-n-propylacetal (AnPA), acetaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal (AnBA), acetaldehyde di-iso-butyl acetal (AiBA), acetaldehyde di-t-butylacetal (AtBA), propionaldehyde diethylacetal (PEA), n-butyraldehyde diethylacetal (nBEA), acetaldehyde dibenzylacetal (ABA), monochloroacetaldehyde diethylacetal (mCAEA) and monochloroacetaldehyde dibenzylacetal (mCABA) were prepared by the standard methods⁵ and were characterised by ir and

pmr spectral data. Refractive index and b.p. of the acetals were compared with the reported values. NCSA with high purity was prepared as described in the literature⁶.

The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions ($[\text{acetal}] \gg [\text{NCSA}]$ in acetic acid (75, 80, 85 and 90%, v/v). The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating NCSA iodometrically at different time intervals at several initial concentrations of the reactants. The reaction followed first order kinetics in $[\text{NCSA}]$.

A typical product analysis was carried out as follows. NCSA in acetic acid was added to ABA and mCABA in aqueous acetic acid separately. The reaction was allowed to proceed to completion as evidenced by no change in titre value with time when the reaction mixture was analysed iodometrically. The oxidised mixture was treated with excess sulphuric acid and sodium bisulphite. The mixture was extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, solvent removed under reduced pressure and the product mixture analysed by glc (Toshniwal, 300°, 3 m, column material SE 30). The products in each case were characterised by direct comparison with the authentic samples as the corresponding esters (benzyl acetate in both cases) along with benzyl chloride. Tlc analysis showed the presence of the corresponding benzyl acetate in both cases along with benzyl chloride.

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